

**ANTI-CRISIS MANAGEMENT AS THE MOST IMPORTANT
COMPONENT TO IMPROVE SUSTAINABILITY AND
DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORGANIZATION**

Abstract. Anti-crisis management is a set of measures for timely identification of symptoms of approaching crisis situations, selection of the most optimal strategies to normalize the situation in the company, prevention of possible threats of crisis, prevention of crisis situations.

Key words: anti-crisis management, organization, management, crisis, strategy, globalization, economics, capital, approaches.

Anti-crisis management is a microeconomic category, a reflection of production relations in relation to a particular enterprise. It is formed at the enterprise level in the form of a set of forms and techniques for implementing anti-crisis procedures.

Economic actions are all kinds of human activities that allow society to provide itself with material resources for life. Further, the processes of development of social and economic systems of SES are subject to cyclic regularity, which leads to the realization of the problems of cyclic development of SES. In the aggregate of such problems, various types of crisis arise. Effective solutions to these problems are realized on the basis of ACS crisis management methods.

It is necessary to understand that at every stage of the development of the organization there is a threat of crisis, even if there is no crisis, that is, in fact there is no crisis. Thus, the management of SES should always be anti-crisis, as a system of prevention of bankruptcy of the enterprise, as a management system in which the problems of bankruptcy prevention are put forward in the foreground.

In economic history, it can be argued that in any organization in the process of evolution, a crisis situation is possible, and also indicates the presence of certain critical factors of deterrence, elimination or activation necessary to continue the process of reproducing the functioning of the organization or to move to a new level of quality.

As a rule, an organization is in a crisis state for quite a long time, when negative factors accumulate. The exit from the crisis can be instantaneous - due to a one-time capital investment, takeover, change of the field of activity, processing, etc., as well as prolonged. K. Marx and G. Engels formulated the theory of economic balance of capitalist competitive market systems of economy in accordance with Newton's ideas about balance.

Such a model of economic development processes allows for a fairly successful analysis of internal factors of organization functioning, as well as, in contrast to external conditions, the development of optimization models of organization management. The disadvantage of this approach is the underestimation of external factors, which, with the simplification of national economic systems, universal information, globalization, are sharply increasing.

Closer to the economic reality presents a model of the functioning of the industrial production firm, taking into account the main factors of the external environment of the direct business and its indirect actions. In this state of affairs, the sustainability of the organization arises not only through internal means, but also through targeted external influences that intensify when the organization moves away from equilibrium. This gives the organization an element of self-regulation by the larger macro system.

Such a model of equilibrium functioning of the organization, in general, satisfies the necessary economic calculations the necessary accuracy, and can be used as a basic model at the micro or macro levels. However, it should not be forgotten that in the development of the organization it is assumed that there is an inequality of factors of counteraction to economic forces, as well as the presence of the factor of progressive directions in the system.

This phenomenon is comparable to the conclusion of the catastrophe theory, which suggests that the economic system should not be equilibrium. In practice, it is manifested by the fact that the industrial enterprise develops, passes through different stages of its life activity (Fig. 1):

Figure 1 - Life cycle of an organization

- 1) growth;
- 2) stabilization;
- 3) stagnation;
- 4) restructuring;
- 5) growth in a new capacity.

At the stage of predominance of one force, when its equalities are not equal to zero, there is a destruction of the system and stagnation in the 3rd stage, turns into restructuring in the 4th stage. Prolonged stay of the organization at the stage of the fourth stage, without pronounced constructive forces, can lead to complete bankruptcy of the organization; the 3rd, 4th and initial parts of the 5th stages of the life cycle of the organization characterize its state of crisis condition, the management of which has specific features that give grounds to allocate it to a special form called "anti-crisis management".

At the 3rd and 4th stages in the process of anti-crisis management there is a redistribution of internal and external potential of the economic organization, resulting in the rebuilding of the equilibrium of a new level of quality. Often, in response to crises, the system itself develops appropriate mechanisms, which are first tested in practice and then theoretically justified. In connection with the situation in Uzbekistan, the greatest interest is the restructuring of the enterprise, experiencing a crisis, which provides solutions aimed at improving performance, changing the management of assets, the use of borrowed financial opportunities.

It should be said that to recognize an organization as a non-payer and unsatisfied with the balance sheet structure does not mean to recognize the organization as bankrupt and, therefore, does not change its legal status. Calculations and assessments of the criteria are preventive, allowing only to state to the owners of the property that the financial condition of the organization is unstable. At the same time, it is clear enough that each organization is able to use various factors to increase its economic potential, to use any, sometimes extraordinary, measures aimed at improving its financial condition: changes in financial policy, increase in asset turnover, growth of sales profitability, etc. The main methods of solving financial crises in the organization are:

- cost reduction;
- increasing cash flow into the organization;
- restructuring of accounts payable;
- determining the organization's development strategy;
- reorganization or restructuring of the organization.

Cost cutting is a necessary step in the face of an organization's financial crisis. It is necessary to centrally make all decisions affecting the movement of the organization's assets and reduce or freeze costs associated with the development of existing projects of long-term perspective: Research and Development Institutes, capital projects and other investments that pay off for more than a year.

Methods of cost reduction include: controlling costs, analyzing the causes of costs, classifying them by degrees of dependence on output, implementing cost reduction measures, and evaluating the result.

Debt restructuring is a process of preparation and execution of a number of consecutive agreements between enterprises and creditors, the main purpose of which is to obtain various types of concessions from creditors: reduction of total

debt: reduction of total debt, exemption from payment of interest, reduction of interest rates, deferral of payment.

Restructuring of organizations is a complex process of preparation and implementation of projects of cardinal changes in the state of existing organizations, their structures, which can be implemented in the form of mergers, acquisitions, divisions, horizontal and vertical integrations. Restructuring requires the development of clear strategies and the formation of a new business strategy of the company, which may lead to a change in the organizational and legal form of the company.

The principle of "reducing the excess" implies the need to reduce the size of both the current need, caused by the corresponding financial liabilities, as well as certain types of liquid asset for urgent conversion into cash forms. This is possible due to:

- accelerating the collection of accounts receivable;
- reduction of the period of granting commodity (commercial) credit;
- reduction of the size of insurance stocks of inventories (inventory);
- markdown of hard-to-liquid types of inventory to the level of the demand price with the provision of their subsequent sale;
- accelerated sale of unused equipment at the demand prices in the relevant market;
- lease of equipment previously planned for acquisition in the process of fixed assets renewal, etc;
- prolongation of short-term financial loans;
- extension of the period of commodity credit provided by suppliers.

Anti-crisis management has features:

- mobility and dynamism in the use of resources, carrying out changes, implementation of innovative programs;
- implementation of program-targeted approaches in the technologies of development and implementation of management decisions;
- increased sensitivity to the time factor in management processes, implementation of timely actions on the dynamics of situations;
- increased attention to preliminary and subsequent assessments of managerial decisions and selection of alternatives of behavior and activity;
- use of anti-crisis criterion of quality of decisions in their development and implementation.

In the mechanism of anti-crisis management, which has its own peculiarities, priorities should be given to:

- motivation, focused on anti-crisis measures, saving resources, avoiding mistakes, caution, deep analysis of situations, professionalism, etc.;
- attitudes to optimism and confidence, social and psychological stability of activity;
- integration on the values of professionalism;

- initiative in solving problems and searching for the best development options;

- corporatism, mutual acceptance, search for and support of innovations.

All this should be reflected in the style of managerial management, characterized by professional confidence, purposefulness, research approach, acceptance of responsibility.

This study analyzed the essence of crisis management at the enterprise level and its importance in the context of economic systems development. The study of the development processes of socio-economic systems allows us to understand the cyclical nature of their changes, which requires the meaningful application of anti-crisis measures to prevent possible crises.

An important conclusion is the need for a constant anti-crisis approach in the management of economic systems at all their stages of development. In addition, it is noted that the exit from the crisis state can be both instantaneous and prolonged, which requires flexibility and an integrated approach to management.

The theoretical foundations of crisis management formulated by K. Marx and F. Engels. Marx and F. Engels, are still relevant, but in modern conditions require additional consideration of external factors such as globalization and informatization.

Thus, the development of crisis management remains an important task to ensure the stable functioning of economic systems and prevent possible crises.

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